

BONGGA KA DAY: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE IDENTITY FORMATION AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF FILIPINO HOMOSEXUAL MALE BREADWINNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 8

Pages: 1052-1076

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2413

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13843179

Manuscript Accepted: 03-23-2023

Bongga Ka Day: A Phenomenological Study on the Identity Formation and Work-Life Balance of Filipino Homosexual Male Breadwinners

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Abstract

A breadwinner is the one obligated to support the family's needs. It requires sacrifice and work-life balance to meet ends. Various studies have shown that many are struggling to keep up with being the sole provider in the household, with the fact that the Philippines has one of the highest income tax rates in the world, what more for those homosexual males who are breadwinners of their family with challenges in revealing their identity? A study by McPhail (2014) expressed that living out your sexual orientation is a double-edged sword for homosexual male workers in terms of their careers. This descriptive phenomenological study focused on the lived experience of homosexual male breadwinners to determine the role their obligation plays in their identity along with its relationship with work-life balance. Following Paul Collaizi's descriptive phenomenological method, the researchers created a structured interview consisting of 10 questions. Purposive and snowball sampling was used to collect data from a total of 15 participants interviewed through Google Meet. The findings show that being a homosexual breadwinner still entails the usual hardships and stress the normal breadwinner goes under. On a positive point, only a few participants experienced discrimination in their careers. It was found that the lived experience of homosexual male breadwinners indeed has an established relationship between identity formation and work-life balance.

Keywords: *breadwinner, homosexual male, identity formation, work-life balance, phenomenological study*

Introduction

Family is the basic structure of society, and the one that is considered as the foundation to help them strive each day are the breadwinners. They are the main provider that supports the family financially. Not all families have the privilege of being complete, so being the breadwinner is deferred to whoever is the most capable and responsible one. This role is commonly occupied by the father, who carries the responsibility of his family as traditional gender norms educate young girls that women are responsible for both the physical and mental labor of completing home duties while in breadwinner positions. On the other hand, educate young boys that masculinity is linked to economic support for the family, as cited by Ruppanner (2018). Being a breadwinner means that they have to always find a way to have a stable income for their family, and that means that they are under a lot of stress. Many are struggling to keep up with just being the solo provider, especially now that the Philippines has one of the highest income tax rates in the world.

Filipinos are known to be family-oriented, as they place a strong value on their family and prioritize it above anything else. They struggle all day and do all in their power to feed and provide for their family, as mentioned by Goyala (2019). There is a rise of homosexuals to be the breadwinner of the family as depicted in the movies. One example is the movie "Oliver", where Oliver, the main protagonist, is a female impersonator who supports her family by working at homosexual clubs in Manila from Art and Education (2020). However, the fact that homosexuality is still not accepted by many just brings discrimination and prejudice to those individuals who belong to the homosexual + community. Activists have been clamoring in pursuit of equality. With the increasing number of homosexual male breadwinners over the years, some of them are still not accepted by their own kin - as shared by a social media post of Jobby (2021) wherein it stated that "The place where they should be most comfortable with is inside their own home because if not they should close ties as they don't deserve to be treated differently by their own family for the reason that they're being themselves and that they're not hurting anybody". That being said, they are clearly promoting empowerment to their fellow homosexuals by just standing as the breadwinner. Hence, they receive respect.

Lloyd Cafe Cadena, Jeremy Sancebuche, known as Mimiyyuuh, and Jose Marie Borja Vical, known as Vice Ganda, are three recognizable public figures in the Philippine entertainment industry. What is common about them is that they are the breadwinners of their families. Mimiyyuuh is a renowned social media celebrity and influencer who expressed his experience as the breadwinner of the family. He emphasized that during their lowest point in life, he claimed that "darating 'yung araw na ako na magp-provide sa pamilya". He manifested this into reality. He exclaimed that "hindi expressive ang family ko, but nakikita ko sa actions nila how happy they are. And for me, that is an indication that I have achieved my goal" Villanueva (2022). Meanwhile, Vice Ganda shared his insight in one blog on how important it is to prioritize building the self first for the family. He emphasized that "Naniniwala ako na kung wala akong lakas sa sarili, hindi ko to mashe-share sa pamilya ko. I built myself first and prioritized that before anything else" Juan (2019). Lastly, Lloyd Cadena was one of the public figures who topped YouTube, representing Filipinos. Lloyd served as an inspiration not only to the LGBTQ+ community but to the whole Philippines. Additionally, he is a breadwinner who had the goal to rush and buy that property he dreamed of for his loving mother, in which he did not want to work overseas again. His manifestation for a worry-free life with her mother was reached before he set forth on earth. He did not only support his family's needs but also helped viewers and even strangers by providing for and supplying their needs. Lloyd Cadena had a good and generous heart and is known for his family values and witty

personality (Elikay, 2020).

It is out of the ordinary in the Philippines to see homosexual men standing up as the breadwinner of the family. The fact that LGBTQ+ community has recently established its place in society but is still not fully embraced as part of it due to its clashes with traditional values and modern views. These public figures who are part of the LGBTQ+ community and are breadwinners of the family gave the researchers the idea to pursue a study in this field.

Additionally, an existing paper discussed that there are no established roles for homosexual men, unlike that of men and women in platforms, except the fact that these individuals are viewed as a source of entertainment and laughter for the viewers according to what was found in the study of Bautista (2019). However, what is extraordinary in the finding of the study is those fellow homosexual men who are well known are seen as inspirations by younger generations belonging to the same community.

Living out to one's sexual orientation is a double-edged sword for homosexual male workers in terms of their careers. Such as in a study by McPhail (2014) wherein the participants expressed that when it comes to their sexual orientation, homosexual males looking for work or a career typically came out to their coworkers at work but kept it a secret from others outside the company. Whether or not to disclose their sexual orientation to their hiring employer or not is a critical state to their career. For some, this led to his application as a barrier to moving forward and being processed, but to others, it is a requirement for the company and people to actually provide them with career opportunities. This supports the study of Allan et al. (2015), who believed that lesbian, gay, or bisexual (LGB) populations are more motivated, which leads to job satisfaction and a sense of purpose in life.

With the existing literature, it is very evident that LGBTQ+ that, includes homosexual males, are establishing rapport in the community. All the while, the community fails to view the roles of homosexual men in comparison to men and women. Homosexual men who are public figures expressing personal experience as breadwinners of the family guided the researchers to fill the gaps of this phenomenon. The researchers decided to pursue this research topic to know the perspectives of homosexual men breadwinners in regard to their role in the family. As Filipinos are known to be tied with traditional family values and religion (Kent & Poushter, 2020), it is a fact that not everyone is open to embracing the LGBTQ+ community as part of the society as a whole due to prevalent homophobia and religious beliefs that may affect these homosexual men's view of themselves.

Leading to the importance of why this study should be conducted, the researchers aim to know the phenomenological experience of homosexual men breadwinners. How these experiences shaped their identity, and how they managed to find the best work-life balance. LGBTQ+ is a community not fully embraced yet in the Philippines. This has given the researchers the interest to give knowledge on society, as a whole, that gender differences do not limit an individual's capacity to be breadwinner. The researchers will construct interview guide questions in order to analyze and interpret the perception of homosexual male breadwinners who will take part in the study. The statements in the test will be formed with open-ended questions to connect with the respondents in a conversational manner.

Research Questions

This study intends to explore the peculiar position of Filipino Homosexual Male breadwinners regarding their work-life balance and identity formation, specifically from their lived experiences. To distinguish the role of financial stability in accordance with career preference, empower homosexual male individuals using their own responsibility and drive as breadwinners. In addition, this study seeks to provide supporting data for policymakers on establishing aid for breadwinners in general. The researchers formulated the following research questions to meet the study's objectives:

1. What are the lived experiences of Filipino Homosexual Male Breadwinners in terms of work-life balance and personal individuality?
2. What is the role of career and finances to Homosexual Males as breadwinners? What drove Filipino Homosexual Male Breadwinners to take up their role in the family?
3. Is there an established relationship between identity formation and work-life balance?

Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of the study is to determine the identity formation of homosexual males amidst being the breadwinners of their families, along with identifying factors on how they balance work and life responsibilities. Along with this, to understand the drives, sacrifices, and financial satisfaction among homosexual males with their role in the family as breadwinners. The researchers are predisposed to cohere an understanding of the lived experience of the participants who will take part in the study.

The study used Paul Colaizzi's Descriptive Phenomenological Method in order to best gather information on how breadwinning shapes the identity of homosexual males along with their work and life balance. This guaranteed the validity and dependability of the research findings. It enabled researchers to identify themes through which the underlying framework of an experience can be investigated is logical and clear (Bakonc et al., 2018). An interpretation of essence is a basic functional explanation of how a phenomenon is experienced (Osroosh, 2021). It aims to describe the phenomenon's structure to provide a deeper, more complete, and holistic understanding of the lived experience. Additionally, thematic network analysis was used in order to transform meaning units in

accordance with the shared experiences of the participants who took part in the study.

Three (3) stages were involved in the study, namely: conceptual, development, and empirical phase. Purposively, these stages served as a guide for the researchers to have an inclined understanding and discovery of this study.

Conceptual Stage: Series of information from literature was discovered by the researchers in this phase. With this, the conceptualization of research objectives was reached in order to study the identity formation of homosexual male breadwinners.

Development Stage: This includes the process of how samples and data was collected, such as but not limited to: Sampling Procedure, Research Locale, Research Instrument, and Data Gathering Procedure.

Empirical Stage: Interpretation of data from data collection and data analysis are accomplished in this stage. With the basis of lived experience among, participants' statements was categorized into themes.

Participants

Participants in the study are Filipino homosexual breadwinners individuals residing in any area of the Philippines. Considering examining the entire population is impossible, researchers will collect information from a drawn sample using a non-probability sampling approach. The participants were selected using purposive and snowball sampling.

Purposive sampling is the purposeful selection of respondents based on their capacity to express a certain theme, subject, or experience (Robinson, R.S., 2014). The type of purposive sampling technique used, to be specific, is a homogenous sample where the participants have a common characteristic (Crossman, A. 2020). Moreover, purposive sampling enables the researchers to interact with respondents for prolonged periods of time, enabling the collection of greater quantities of data than would be practicable with probability sampling.

Snowball sampling, on the other hand, is a non-probability sampling method in which current research participants help recruit future study participants (Simkus, J. 2022). To be more specific, the snowball sampling method chosen is exponential non-discriminative snowball sampling, with the initial participant referring to several connections. In other words, the researcher identifies the first participant, who then recruits multiple more (Nikolopoulou, K. 2022). Each additional referral provides the researchers with more possible research candidates. This geometric chain sampling cycle continues until the study has the target number of participants (Simkus, J. 2022).

A breadwinner is a household's primary or lone income earner. Breadwinners pay the majority of home costs and financially support their families by providing a large amount of household income. The breadwinner paid a minimum of half of the total household costs, which include rent or mortgage payments, electric bills, health coverage, taxes, food, and maintenance (Kagan, J. 2023).

Homosexual male refers to intimate relationships, sexual desire, or physical intimacy between people of a similar sexual orientation or gender. Homosexuality is defined as a longstanding cycle of feelings of affection, sexual desire, or both toward individuals of the same gender. It often implies someone's perception of self-identity determined by those interests, associated actions, and engagement in the group that includes other people who reflect those points of interest (Handwiki,2022).

In total, 15 participants were interviewed using a structured questionnaire. Once data saturation is reached; that also is, enough information has been gathered to draw a valid conclusion, and thus further collected data will not generate important additional insight. Accordingly, the qualified participants in the study are:

Filipino citizens

Homosexual Male

Breadwinner

Instrument

The researchers decided to conduct the interview via Google Meet due to its simple and accessible nature, which makes it more convenient for both the researchers and the participants. No physical contact was made, ensuring the participants' comfort and safety. Furthermore, the researchers conducted interviews via email follow-up should further inquiries be necessary regarding their responses.

Procedure

To successfully accomplish the objectives of the study, the following procedures were observed in the collection of data and management. Some documents were first processed through validation for the adviser to provide their perceptions. The researchers then generated an online consent form which was filled up with the use of google forms. This was used to ask permission from the respondents in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Once the participants had accomplished filling up the consent form, the researchers scheduled an online recorded interview with each one of the respondents, utilizing Google Meet as an instrument to conduct the interviews. After the data was retrieved successfully from the selected participants, the researchers utilized the information needed for their study.

Data Analysis

The process of data analysis that the researchers employed in this study was as follows: interpreting and evaluating the data manually by transcribing the interview of the participants word-by-word. For this study, the researchers utilized Paul Collaizi's (1978, as cited in Wirihana et al., 2018) descriptive phenomenological method of analyzing data. First, the researchers carefully transcribed all the participants' descriptions from the interview. The second step is identifying the significant statements connected to the study. The third step is the formation of formulated meaning from the statements of the participants, and the fourth is identifying the potential themes from the significant statements provided by the participants. Afterward, the fifth step consists of establishing cluster themes from the formulated meaning. The sixth step consists of identifying the fundamental structure that incorporates phenomena based on their respective themes and producing a statement that is ever-present in the phenomenon explored. Lastly, the seventh step consists of members checking and validating of analysis with participants. (Morrow et al., 2015).

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Ethical Considerations

In compliance with ethical concerns for this study, interested participants were provided informed consent. The researchers explained the procedure to the participants, and then they understood how the data would be collected. Participants may ask questions and voice concerns regarding the study. More importantly, they have the option to participate in or deny the interview. Participants have the option of not revealing their identities in the data collection, analysis, and discussions of the study's conclusions to better secure the information they provide. They were scheduled separately in a private setting without other people who were not part of the data gathering process online.

The researchers ensured that the respondents were allowed to react honestly and without feeling pushed to do so. Furthermore, in compliance with the 2012 Data Privacy Act, the researchers assured that necessary consent was gained from respondents via a signed agreement, and anonymity was guaranteed for any personal information submitted to them by respondents during the procedure. The data included, gathered, processed, communicated, disclosed, and stored in this format was kept private and was just for the purpose of the researchers. To protect the researchers' anonymity, the data obtained were transcribed and processed in encrypted documents protected by privacy access, coded and assessed by the researchers to discover themes and reduce biases, and available only to the researchers. Following that, the recordings and information will be saved and discarded once the research is completed.

Results and Discussion

Emergent Theme #1: Personal Perspective of Family Connectedness

Interview Question: As the homosexual breadwinner, how would you describe your position in the family in relation to your connection with them?

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>
1	“Yung mother ko kasi my mudra, is a uhn solo parent and due to the pandemic last 2 years ago and nawalan siya ng trabaho a factory worker kaya since then ayun ako nalang ang nag provide for the family.” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 4-7)	Sole provider shouldering responsibilities.
2	“I am accountable in making sure my family gets the basic needs in their lives along with other necessities that help improve their health and wellbeing.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 3-5)	Accountable for family needs.
3	“medyo mataas yung tingin nila sa akin kasi like uhh kahit papaano malaki naman natutulong ko sa bahay, uhm then hindi ko nararanasan yung discrimination sa magulang ko pero alam ko naman na hindi pa nila like tanggap fully.” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 3-5)	Respect from assistance.
4	“They’ve accepted me for who I am, and I’m lucky for that. However, some things have changed when I came out to them so like uhm the daily basis, the daily interaction have changed, Well my siblings have always been very supportive. But in terms of my parents, there’s still some awkwardness.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 3-6)	Increase approval in exchange for service.
5	“Maganda kasi natutuwa nanay ko sakín lalo na kasi malaki natutulong ko sa gastusin bilang secretary. Mas may respeto din sila sa sexuality ko (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 3-4)	Breadwinning increased the respect for sexuality in the family.

6	“I consider myself to have a special position in my family as the homosexual breadwinner. “The relationship I have with my family members is still solid and unconditional, despite the fact that my sexual orientation adds a degree of complication to the typical family dynamic. The love and care I require to succeed have always been given to me, and they have consistently been supportive and tolerant of my identity.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 3-7)	Unique position as the family provider and homosexual in the family Increase support and approval
7	“I describe my position to be more on natural, at first, I was anxious if they would be able to accept me, we had lots of fights and misunderstanding but when we both try to reconnect, we now able to understand each other and try to support one another in a way we can.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 3-5)	Respondent feel anxious at the beginning of being open as a homosexual in the family.
8	“I am a provider also I stand as the breadwinner.” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 3)	Position in the family did not necessarily impact the relationship yet stands as a family provider.
9	“I have a very close relationship with all of them. Usually, my siblings would seek help and support from me, while our parents support the decisions I make as the breadwinner. (Participant 9, Transcript I, Lines 3-5)	The respondent is very close to each member of the family and the family supports the decision that makes as the breadwinner.
10	“Being open to them about my gender was a difficult yet fulfilling memory for me. And uhm as a breadwinner I believe that through providing for my family’s needs I feel like somehow slowly but surely they are accepting who I am as a homosexual male and it is something I look forward to — to be accepted fully po.” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Line 3-7)	The significance of gender acceptance of family and self is fulfilling.
11	“Being the sole provider is very exhausting as I do not have any rest, but seeing my family be happy is enough for me to be motivated again.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 5-6)	Sole provider in the family.
12	“I struggled in the beginning after coming out when I have not proven myself.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Line 3)	Challenged with family acceptance of sexual identity.
13	“Serves as the family provider that is why they respect me and accepts me because they know I am a good person even if I am homosexual.” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Lines 3-4)	Family provider, acceptance, and respect.
14	“At first, I was not accepted for what I am but as time goes on, they accept and love me and I help them because I am the only one who provides financial support to my family ” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 3-4)	No acceptance in the beginning, but as time goes on, the family accepts and gives love.
15	“The connection between them, between me and the family is crucial regardless of what my sex is, communication, mutual support and respect are all essential components of a strong family unit (sighs) and me as I am the breadwinner is it is an (corrects himself) important role in maintaining this connection by providing the financial stability and support.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 8-12)	Regardless of gender and sexuality, respect is essential especially within the family.

In the Philippines, traditions and organized religion are deeply ingrained in the culture and society. It can be assumed, with many bases, that LGBT folk experience life more difficult than heterosexual people. Of the time, it is the very guardians tasked to protect them who fail to protect and, to some extent, enact the abuse themselves, regardless of the legality of their age (UNDP, USAID 2014.) However, bearing the responsibility of being the breadwinner comes with merit and nobility, as 6 of the respondents shared an increase in nobility that comes with their responsibilities to their families.

“I consider myself to have a special position in my family as the homosexual breadwinner. The relationship I have with my family members is still solid and unconditional, despite the fact that my sexual orientation adds a degree of complication to the typical family dynamic. The love and care I require to succeed have always been given to me, and they have consistently been supportive and tolerant of my identity.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 3-7)

The other 5 felt the increase in respect and approval but without full acceptance due to their sexuality. Of course, old habits die hard, and even more so when it comes to traditions and culture, for these traditions reigned over familial relationships. As it is quite customary for the parents of our generation to shun such unconventional lifestyles because they themselves grew up in a time when being homosexual was much even more taboo. (Casal, 2019)

“At first, I was not accepted for what I am but as time goes on, they accept and love me and I help them because I am the only one who provides financial support to my family” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 3-4)

The rest of them, four respondents, see their position in the family with honor and wear it on their sleeve. They take great pride in being the provider in their respective families.

“I am accountable in making sure my family gets the basic needs in their lives along with other necessities that help improve their health and wellbeing.” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 3-5)

Emergent Theme #2: The Impact of Breadwinning on Personal Identity

Interview Question: What is the impact of your obligations and responsibility to your identity?

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>
1	“it’s a conflict to me at first kasi diba ano dalawa e, pero you know as life goes on I started to ano na believe in myself (pause) and ano pa kaya (short pause) and ano na embrace ko naman siya due to the responsibility i have to provide for my family naman since i have to work like a mother ay ay ay.. no, i have to work like a father and at the same time caring naman like a mother sa mga siblings ko.” (Participant 1 Transcript A line 18-23)	learning to embrace responsibility.
2	“Honestly It can be stressful and distressing at times. As most people may be aware of, there are some discrimination towards homosexual people one way or another.” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 10-12)	Prejudice towards homosexual people.
3	“like accepted naman nila yung ganun tapos enjoy sila sa kapag nagpapatawa ako ganun may mga alitan minsan pero part naman yun nang pagkakaibigan eh basta masaya pa rin. Pero like sa family ano like may times na okay naman siya may times parang weirded out pero di pa naman sya like big big the problem ganun.” (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 13-17)	Sense of belongingness.
4	“me...It made me understand the real meaning of self love and I think that even tho I love myself for who I am it’s also important to provide for my family” (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 10-11)	Self-love and love for family.
5	“Dahil sa tulong ko sa bahay mas may respeto siya sa akin kaya mas may freedom ako gawin ang gusto ko.Mas naging confident ako sa sarili ko.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 6-8)	Personal Development of maturity, responsibility and interpersonal relationships
6	“In the end, being a gay breadwinner may be both an honor and a burden.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 17-18)	Facing discrimination and burden impacts identity and dedication.
7	“I think my obligations help me shape how I see life; it made me confident that I have a place at home and was able to build my own small circle of friends that truly accepts me.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Lines 10-11)	Obligation and responsibility challenged the respondent to become strong and optimistic and can express life freely.
8	“I stand as a breadwinner they looked at me like I am the family provider.” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 6-7)	Being a breadwinner and having an identity both set expectations from my family.
9	“I find myself as someone who’s very independent, but really soft when it comes to my family.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Line 7-8)	Taking obligations and responsibility is hard, but making the family happy gives them the power to enjoy that.
10	“Being part of the LGBTQ+ community molds me positively in a way that I become more confident and accountable to function not only within the house but also in terms of socially interacting with others. I believe that this has increased my social skills which is very important for me to distress and not be over loaded with work.” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Line 9-13)	Obligations developed an accountable, confident, and socially active personal identity.
11	“That I have to give them the best of what I can do for them to accept me. Hindi na nila 'to ginagawa ngayon pero naisip ko pa rin na dapat gawin ko ang best ko for them.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Line 8-9)	Drive to perform obligations is to receive acceptance in the family.
12	“left to take care of your parents. I feel like I don’t have my own purpose to live besides supporting my parents.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Line 7-8)	Selfless identity, altruistic personality.
13	“The impact of my obligations is it helped me to be more responsible and matured because I know what will I prioritize first.” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Lines 6-7)	Enhanced maturity from obligations.
14	“Impact? Not sure but maybe I'm tired of my responsibility. I have taken on many obligations and responsibilities and now I am at a point where I feel tired.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 6-7)	The respondent feels exhausted from carrying out the obligations and responsibilities.
15	“Our obligations and responsibilities shape our identity, and how we can fulfill them can either strengthen or challenge ourselves.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 15-16)	Being a breadwinner helped me to be stronger.

Being entrusted with the integral position of the breadwinner, whether by choice or not, disrupts one's own plans, dreams, and even personality. There isn't time to think over if the path aligns with the personality they have or they're working towards. Not when there is a need for a provider in the family, and they are the ones best to take up the task. This portion seeks to discover the relationship between the respondents' obligations along with their personalities. The majority, nine of the respondents, reported that their responsibilities have had a positive impact on their personality. This group mentioned an increase in their independence particularly. They thrive in the environment they are in, especially regarding their colleagues. This is congruent to the experiences of a seafarer, a line of work in which men dominate the ranks. A change of positive mindset focused on bravery, dedication, and perseverance does wonders for homosexual employees (Lagniton, 2022).

“Dahil sa tulong ko sa bahay mas may respeto siya sa akin kaya mas may freedom ako gawin ang gusto ko. Mas naging confident ako sa sarili ko.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 6-8)

Two respondents said that their obligation became an avenue for discrimination which in turn decreased their sense of self-worth. This is also inclusive of workplace discrimination that LGBT folk are so vulnerable to. To these respondents, there is a certain air of unfairness in the life they are thrust into.

“Honestly It can be stressful and distressing at times. As most people may be aware of, there is some discrimination towards homosexual people one way or another.” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 10-12)

Another two respondents have felt acceptance from their peers and their respective circles. In their families, their obligations have turned into a driver and motivation.

“Like accepted naman nila yung ganun tapos enjoy sila sa kapag nagpapatawa ako ganun may mga alitan minsan pero part naman yun nang pagkakaibigan eh basta masaya pa rin. Pero like sa family ano like may times na okay naman siya may times parang weirded out pero di pa naman sya like big big the problem ganun.” (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 13-17)

The last two of them expressed exhaustion from the work put in. The development of their personalities and sense of identity may be hampered by the constant application of stress on their mental well-being.

“Impact? Not sure but maybe I'm tired of my responsibility. I have taken on many obligations and responsibilities and now I am at a point where I feel tired.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 6-7)

Emergent Theme #3: Values Developed from Breadwinning Role

Interview Question: How do you think your role in the family, alongside your sexual identity, shape the outlook you have in life?

Participants	Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning
1	“I have those terms and responsibilities currently on my shoulders kasi like saakin dapat and i take it naman as blessings as disguise for I become more (statter) optimistic and ambitious in life, i'm very motivated din to do more, to do more not only for myself especially sa family ko talaga.” (Participant 1 Transcript A line 27-30)	Optimistic view on responsibilities.
2	“I need to love myself first and foremost and when people see that na no matter what they say about me na I still love myself ganoon parang I'm able to vibrate that characteristic onto my personality and alam mo yun parang people will see that and parang they will see na there's nothing wrong with me naman parang I'm just human just like everyone else and therefore makikita nila na ano there's nothing wrong with people like me, there's nothing to fear alam mo yun.” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 23-29)	Self Love and Acceptance.
3	“kasi parang balance yan eh uh mas-masyahin at palaging tumatawa naman kapag nakikihalubilo ako sa mga friends or co-workers ko so minsan nakakatanggal ng stress pero ano sa work ko naman since ako nga yung breadwinner malaking obligation sa akin yun.” (Participant 3 Transcript C Line 21-24)	Maintaining jolly personality in midst of pressure from responsibility.
4	“It exposes you to the cruelty and at the same time beauty of the world. So it has opened my mind to whatever this life gives... Taught me to be open-minded and strong.” (Participant 4 Transcript D Line 17-18,21)	Challenges stimulate growth.
5	““big part ang obligation ko na maging masipag para sa kanila yun yung outlook ko sa buhay bigyan sila ng magandang buhay since di ko sila mabibigyan ng apo in the future” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 12-14)”	Responsibility and obligation to their family developed a positive outlook in life.
6	“Has taught me to be understanding, to accept others' differences, and to be forgiving.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Lines 29-30)	Sexual Identity results in being optimistic.
7	“I think my role in my family became my standing point for who I am today”(Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 16)	The family treated him normally and gave him support.
8	“Negatively po siguro yung nagiging outlook ko kase sometimes I felt that they only are proud of me if I was able to achieve something big.” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Lines 10-11)	Expectations of achievements shape the outlook in life negatively.
9	“I 've constantly thought about my family first before myself.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Lines 11-12)	The sexual identity is not affecting his role in the family.
10	“I believe that looking on the positive side of everything is healthy as this promotes more positivity and eliminate most negative thoughts that are unnecessary especially to me who has a significant role in the family.” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Lines 18-20)	The sexual identity is not affecting his role in the family.
11	“Tingin ko kailangan talaga may patunayan ang isang taong member ng LGBTQ community para matanggap kami ng aming pamilya.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 12-13)	As an LGBTQ+ member, I need to prove myself to receive acceptance from my family.
12	“All the pressure and discrimination that comes with it made me stronger. I strived to be	Struggles led to a strong and

13	more successful and independent.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 12-13) “I think it made my outlook in life to be more tough and strong, to work harder for things I want to accomplish and to help myself and family.” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Lines 10-11)	optimistic outlook. Developed a strong and tough outlook in life with perseverance.
14	“I became strong because when I get scared, I couldn't provide for my family's needs.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 10)	The respondent needs to become strong in being able to provide for the family's needs.
15	“factors can influence our sense of duty, motivations and fulfillment in our life. Overall our obligations and responsibilities can shape our identity in positive and negative ways. That’s it.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, line 32-34)	Obligation and sexual identity shape the outlook of life.

Suffering builds and alters character. Having a responsibility as crucial as being the breadwinner reshapes the outlook one has in life due to the weight of the burden and the shifting of priorities that come with bearing that responsibility. With this question asked to the five respondents, it is conclusive that the challenge and pressure are something to be expected. With challenge comes growth and development, and the group observed the development of a stronger sense of being and humbleness.

“Tingin ko kailangan talaga may patunayan ang isang taong member ng LGBTQ community para matanggap kami ng aming pamilya.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 12-13)

Four respondents reported how their responsibilities gave them the capability to develop a positive outlook in life. It is the most positive take the respondents have had regarding this question. This a prime example of how suffering and hardships can be used for positive development in character. Very much like when internet personality Lloyd Cadena used his fame and the fortune that came with it to help his family, particularly his mother, who raised him. He never let go of his being family-oriented despite his very alluring explosive success (Elikay, 2020).

“Big part ang obligation ko na maging masipag para sa kanila yun yung outlook ko sa buhay bigyan sila ng magandang buhay since di ko sila mabibigyan ng apo in the future.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 12-14)

Three respondents stated how their roles were challenging, but it resulted in them strengthening their resolve, looking introspectively, and exhibiting a better acceptance of one’s identity. Basically, have a stronger connection with themselves via self-love.

“I need to love myself first and foremost and when people see that na no matter what they say about me na I still love myself ganoon parang I’m able to vibrate that characteristic onto my personality and alam mo yun parang people will see that and parang they will see na there’s nothing wrong with me naman parang I’m just human just like everyone else and therefore makikita nila na ano there’s nothing wrong with people like me, there’s nothing to fear alam mo yun.” (Participant 2 Transcript B Line 23-29)

Two of the respondents reported a more altruistic and selfless change in their outlook on life.

“I have those terms and responsibilities currently on my shoulders kasi like saakin dapat and i take it naman as blessings as disguise for I become more (statter) optimistic and ambitious in life, i'm very motivated din to do more, to do more not only for myself especially sa family ko talaga.” (Participant 1 Transcript A line 27-30)

The last respondent said that it gave them a sense of humbleness and gratitude, choosing to thank their hardship and obligations for molding the person they are today.

“I think my role in my family became my standing point for who I am today.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 16)

Emergent Theme #4: Satisfaction or Frustration towards Breadwinning Role in relation to Sexual Identity

Interview Question: How satisfying or frustrating is it to you being the breadwinner of the family at the same time homosexual?

Participants	Significant statement	Formulated meaning
1	“at first, ung pagiging breadwinner ko talaga parang ano sobrang bigat kasi sakin pero you know as time goes on naman na talaga matured na ako like for 3 years i've been working na parang accept nii accept ko na sya na before it become more satisfying pa na nafufulfil ko ung mga gusto ko magawa para sa family ko at maafford lahat ang kailagan nila at niacknowledge naman nila ako.” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 41-46)	Learning to love responsibilities and obligations with support from family
2	“Amongst all the challenges in life, I think na masaya ako that I am more than happy to be able to help my family” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 38-39)	Satisfied with helping family
3	“mix of both siya like satisfying and frustrating kasi ano masaya ako na i feel important gawa nga nang pagtulong ko sa magulang ko at nakikita ko silang maginhawa parang ganun like nafefeel ko naman na nahehelp ko sila in some way, especially sa expenses sa bahay. Pero may times na frustrating siya kasi minsan hindi ko nafocus yung sarili ko” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 32-36)	An Increased sense of purpose
4	“I know that my parents still love me but I feel different and that’s why I feel like I have to make up to them all the time. I think that’s	Feeling Inadequate

	the frustrating, Frustrating part of feeling different and trying to prove something because you feel you have disappointed them and disappointed yourself.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 31-34)	
5	“Super satisfying kasi mas may freedom akong ilantad sarili sa family ko.” (Participant 5, Transcript D, Line 21)	Self-perception of satisfaction in terms of
6	“It can be satisfying because it is an opportunity to provide for loved ones and make sure that they are taken care of, and it can be frustrating” (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 42-43)	freedom in expressing sexuality The opportunity to provide additional pressure made it both satisfying and frustrating.
7	“I was frustrated at first when we are having misunderstanding as I couldn’t be honest with my family, but being honest and open with them was the start of my most satisfying life being homosexual” (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 25-27)	The respondent felt frustrated in the beginning being open as a homosexual male, but being honest, you feel satisfied for being a homosexual.
8	“I feel like it is frustrating because I got loads of responsibility that makes it harder for me to live.” (Participant 8, Transcript H Line 19-20)	Responsibilities result in frustration and affect other people.
9	“It satisfies me knowing that I get to help my family. However sometimes, I think about myself too.” (Participant 9, Transcript I Line 20-21)	Help the family in terms of financial support from the respondent is given satisfaction, but in the other place he forgets to give love to himself.
10	“I believe that all my efforts and sacrifices are worth it.” (Participant 10, Transcript J Line 28)	Worthwhile satisfaction in terms of obligations in the family.
11	“para saakin satisfying siya kahit na madaming challenges sa paligid,” (Participant 11, Transcript K Line 19)	The breadwinning role is satisfying amidst all challenges.
12	“positive in terms of self fulfillment negative in terms of feeling I am left alone with the responsibilities and that you can’t be weak and must remain invulnerable.” (Participant 12, Transcript L Line 19-20)	The satisfaction due to self-fulfillment and frustration due to feeling of isolation
13	“It is satisfying because I can provide for my family but it is frustrating sometimes because there are times like they rely on me they think I will provide for them forever like It is my only obligation” (Participant 13, Transcript M Line 17-19)	Satisfaction as a sole provider and frustration as to the feeling of long-term obligation.
14	“I’m happy because I’m helping my family’s needs, it’s annoying because sometimes I don’t have any savings for myself.” (Participant 14, Transcript N Line 15-16)	The respondent is satisfied with helping the family’s needs but feels frustrated for not having savings for himself.
15	“It’s important to have a supportive and accepting family and especially community to overcome these challenges and to fulfill a happy life”. (Participant 15, Transcript O Line 50-52)	A supportive environment helps to overcome struggles

Satisfaction or Frustration towards Breadwinning Role in Relation to Sexual Identity

Obligations aren't void of rewards and feelings of satisfaction, which lie in productivity. These benefits gained from work and effort are not limited to money but also extended in the form of non-monetary gain, such as the feeling of fulfillment and satisfaction (Sacristan, 2014). Of course, feelings of satisfaction do not diminish feelings of frustration, both of which could take hold in an individual, particularly for heavy obligations. A total of six respondents answered with feelings of sole satisfaction in their honest work.

“Amongst all the challenges in life, I think na masaya ako that I am more than happy to be able to help my family.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 38-39)

Six respondents reported feelings of both frustration and satisfaction, which is innate in the position held. Being a breadwinner is a constant challenge of stress and reward, putting the work in and getting necessary resources out of their effort. We can see this as LGB folks gaining a sense of purpose, particularly from their job satisfaction due to the steady stream of financial resources they can utilize to help around their households and families. The frustration part can be interpreted as the stress that is innate in working, plus the additional pressure from being the breadwinner of the family (Allan et al., 2015).

“I know that my parents still love me but I feel different and that’s why I feel like I have to make up to them all the time. I think that’s the frustrating, Frustrating part of feeling different and trying to prove something because you feel you have disappointed them and disappointed yourself.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 31-34)

Three respondents stated that they feel nothing but frustration. Being the breadwinner is an additional burden on their part without the satisfaction of balancing the feelings of frustration.

“I was frustrated at first when we are having misunderstanding as I couldn’t be honest with my family, but being honest and open with them was the start of my most satisfying life being a homosexual.” (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 25-27)

The data yielded an integral part of the answer for the first sub-question of the research question—What are the characteristics of Filipino homosexual males who are breadwinners in their family? — which could be concluded as relationships and engagement with family could bring about a source of accomplishment which comes with it a sense of satisfaction. An overall positive revelation.

Emergent Theme #5: Impact of Gender Sensitivity in Workplace towards Identity

Interview Question: How has being homosexual in the workplace and in general affected your identity?

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statement</i>	<i>Formulated meaning</i>
1	“personally kasi wala naman masyadong conflict dun instead na nihelp niya ako na to accept more as i have learned na there are more people like me na hindi ako nag iisa. (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 34-36)	Feeling of belongingness
2	“Pero meron naman na let’s say parang nagloloook down saiyo or parang they don’t get too close because of how they perceive me to be pero it comes with the territory, so i’m kinda used to it, you know ganoon talaga.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 32-35)	Setting boundaries for people who don’t acknowledge homosexuality
3	“okay naman sila like gusto nila ako kasama dahil palajoke nga ako tapos nakikisakay din naman ako sa trip nila so ayun di naman siya like bad affection ganun, masaya sya. (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 27-29)	Belonging to a jolly personality
4	“if there’s one thing that changed it would be that uhm I become stronger and free to show who I truly am. Also, embracing my sexuality exposed me to narrow-minded people and that helped me to find & choose the right people to interact with.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 23-26)	Embracing their sexuality
5	“boss kong homophobic. minsan nagcocomment siya sa news or what na may kinalaman sa lgbt pero masama ang sinasabi kaya nagdadalawang isip ako magout dahil sa kanya.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 16-18)	Negative judgment in the workplace resulted in feelings of judgment.
6	“a greater sense of self-acceptance and promote personal growth.” (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 37- 38)	Homosexuality can be a source of shame yet can lead to self-acceptance and growth.
7	“My workplace is very welcoming; I didn't have any problems dealing with anyone” (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 20)	The workplace gives fair treatment and no discrimination so that you can express yourself freely.
8	“I feel like sometimes po people tends to judge us” (Participant 8, Transcript H Line 14)	Homosexuality tends to affect judgment from other people.
9	“The reason why I always find the need to adjust is because I am trying to avoid getting harassed or discriminated.” (Participant 9, Transcript I Line 15-16)	Respondent experience harassment and discrimination in every place that he goes and has adjusted to being able to work.
10	“sometimes I still feel that I am being judged in the workplace. But somehow i think this will not affect my identity as a person because I have build myself to just let them be” (Participant 10, Transcript J Line 22-23)	Positive self-value amidst judgment in the workplace.
11	“open naman ang work place ko sa mga LGBTQ community, and sa tingin ko naka-epkto to sa magandang social skills ko sa kapwa tao.” (Participant 11, Transcript K Line 15-16)	Peers in the workplace are open to LGBTQ+ co-workers
12	“enhanced my social skills in communicating with people not only in the workplace but in general.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Line 16)	Workplace-enriched social identity
13	“It made me feel anxious and I make sure to be careful when interacting with others because not everyone like gay” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Line 13-14)	Anxiety and cautious identity in the workplace.
14	“Nothing it really did not bother me” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 12)	Being homosexual in the workplace does not have an effect on their identity.
15	“being a homosexual breadwinner in a family that values traditional gender roles may lead to feeling of isolation and conflicts being you know alone and all while being openly accepted and supported by a family may foster a sense of confidence and self-worth.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 41-43)	Confidence can be gained through acceptance

There's a certain comfort in the fact that call center organizations are quite well-known to be welcoming to LGBT+ people, in a way that discrimination is at least minimized somewhat compared to other industries. In the Philippines, wherein call center work is very prevalent and has been steadily going strong over the years, it is possible to conclude that workplace discrimination is proportionally less present, at least in that sector of the labor industry. Rightfully so, discrimination leads to toxic environments, which leads to the employee quitting. Turnover is expensive, and organizations that lose talented employees due to negative workplace experiences not only perpetuate these forms of inequality (Cech & Rothwell, 2019). The researchers set out to find out the exact state of LGBT discrimination in the workplace, and from 15 responses, 10 of them stated a non-negative, or at least neutral, energy in their answers to the question regarding workplace discrimination. Two respondents stated that their sexuality had been welcomed by their peers and colleagues, which led them to embrace their sexual identity more. This is congruent with the study that was conducted centered on

diversity management and how it contributes to shaping the experiences of homosexual employees by ultimately lowering incidents of discrimination and increasing the overall well-being of said employees (Loren & Parini, 2017).

“... okay naman sila like gusto nila ako kasama dahil palajoke nga ako tapos nakikisakay din naman ako sa trip nila so ayun di naman siya like bad affection ganun, masaya sya.” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 27-29)

Another one answered that they had felt a change in their peers' attitudes towards them. The change they felt is so minimal that it doesn't affect their performance. However, there are still unsettling feelings for them.

“Nothing, it really did not bother me in my workplace and also in general.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 12)

Five other respondents go about this question with an introspective attitude. In which they gained a sense of self-acceptance and a deeper appreciation of value.

“connecting with people who share similar experiences and identities. This can lead to a greater sense of self-acceptance and promote personal growth.” (Participant 6, Transcript F Line 37- 38)

Two of the respondents felt an improvement in their social skills. This could be attributed to the fact that they would need to put in extra effort as an outsider to the norm in the workplace, which ultimately resulted in their favor.

“open naman ang work place ko sa mga LGBTQ community, and sa tingin ko naka-epekto to sa 16 magandang social skills ko sa kapwa tao.” (Participant 11, Transcript K Line 15-16)

The last five of the respondents claim that they have felt an air of judgment from their colleagues and peers, which is to be expected in a workplace to have some form of discrimination towards LGBT members.

“Pero meron naman na let's say parang nagloolook down saiyo or parang they don't get to close because of how they perceive me to be pero it comes with the territory so i'm kinda used to it you know ganoon talaga.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 32-35)

The coming data is essential to answering the third sub-question of the research question—Is there an established relationship between work-life balance and identity formation? — which shifts in favor of “yes.” There is an impact between work and identity formation because it is reasonable to conclude that if a person is under duress on the regular at work due to different stressors, it affects their identity. The conditions could make them lean into being introverted or extroverted, depending on the situation, for example.

Emergent Theme #6: Personal Values in Managing Work-Life Balance

Interview Question: What values do you always remind yourself of in managing your work-life balance?

Participants	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning
1	“kailagan kong paalala din na dapat diba work and life lang na ibalance mo lang talaga sya like syempre you have to splurge a little bit for yourself and you know for the family as well at the same time naman thankful din ako sa family ko kasi ano ahh I can extend my help... my help din naman and since ayaw nila ako mastress ng sobra sa work kailangan ko din itake care and sarili ko” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 52-56)	Family support and self-care
2	“As long as I have no negative intentions to anyone, I am good naman saka ano lang parang I need to make time for my family and not only on work.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 44-45)	No malicious thoughts and give time to family
3	“everything is best in moderation naman like friends, works, gala chika, siguro pinakamalaki dito yung ano time management ko ganun.” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 39-40)	Time management
4	“learning to say no and always prioritize your mental and physical health.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 36-37)	Taking care of oneself
5	“Always keep your faith in god. Madalas nagdadasal ako for guidance and when i have a problems sa work or personal life” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 25-26)	Keeping faith in god is a way to cope with work and life balance
6	“to prioritize my mental and physical health. “ (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 49)	Work-Life Balance of self-care
7	“I always remind myself that there will always be "what ifs" if I don't start doing things.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 31)	There is real regret at first when you don't try what you want to do it in life.
8	“Sa tingin ko to take a rest.” (Participant 8, Transcript H Line 23)	Taking rest and health is helpful.
9	“I always tell myself to always look at the brighter side of things no matter how difficult a situation may be.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Line 25-26)	Always think positive no matter how difficult our life is and have a break for ourselves.
10	“I prioritize self-care from time to time.” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Line 30)	Work-Life Balance of self-care
11	“na ginagawa ko ito para sa pamilya ko.” (Participant 11, Transcript K Line 22)	Motivation to meet obligations for the family.
12	“No one will take care of myself so I need to be okay and set my priorities properly. I	Resiliency and task management

13	need to work to live not live to work.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Line 22-23) “take care of myself more and manage my time wisely so I can manage both my work without affecting my personal life” (Participant 13, Transcript M Line 21-22)	Self-care and time management.
14	“To always be thankful and appreciate everything I have and to stay positive in life and have faith in God.” (Participant 14, Transcript N Line 18-19)	Give thanks to God and appreciate everything that you have.
15	“Prioritizing tasks and responsibilities can help focus the most important ones and manage time effectively,clear boundaries between work and your own personal life can help avoid burnout and you know maintaining a healthy balance within work and personal life,being flexible and adaptable to change in work and personal life can help manage unexpected situations therefore it reduces stress, prioritizing self-care by you know by exercising, meditating or different hobbies can help reduce stress, effective communication with colleagues, supervisors, family members, friends helps manage expectation and avoid conflicts, regular reflection and evaluation of one's priorities and goals can help maintain a healthy balance between personal life and work. (Participant 15, Transcript O Line 54-64)	Prioritization, setting boundaries, flexibility,self-care, communication and regular reflection help manage work-life balance

The concept of work-life balance is applicable to anyone working, including members of the LGBT community. This is a question that could be posted anywhere around the world where there are LGBT employees. Although there has been significant progress in extending major benefits to lesbian and gay federal government employees, there continue to be discrepancies between benefits awarded to straight couples and homosexual couples. The researchers asked the same question to the respondents and got nothing but positive responses with varying reasons regarding how they were coping. Seven of them cope with work-life balance by channeling their energy onto taking care of themselves in various and preferred ways. A well-balanced work and life aspects in life are important not only for one reason but several. Their overall contentment with life and the pleasures that come with it is very crucial, along with how it also affects productivity and output at work (Wedgwood, 2022).

“... learning to say no and always prioritize your mental and physical health.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 36-37)

Three of the respondents cope with stress through time management and task compartmentalization.

“uhh everything is best in moderation naman like friends, works, gala chika, 40. siguro pinakamalaki dito yung ano time management ko ganun.” (Participant 3, Transcript C,Line 39-40)

Two of the respondents focus on keeping a positive mental attitude toward their stress management.

“I always remind myself that there will always be "what ifs" if I don't start doing things.” (Participant 7, Transcript G Line 31)

One respondent is out to focus on balancing out the stress with motivators motivation.

“Na ginagawa ko ito para sa pamilya ko.” (Participant 11, Transcript K Line 22)

Finally, the last two responded with faith in their mind. As a deeply religious country, faith and spirituality have been a major aspect of people's lives.

“To always be thankful and appreciate everything I have and to stay positive in life and have faith in God.” (Participant 14, Transcript N Line 18-19)

Of course, this data already answers the question of the respondent's attitude toward their identity formation and work-life balance. Coping with stress and duress gained from regularly putting in an honest day's work reveals much in people and ultimately becomes the path formed by habits and thoughts which shape their overall identity and personality.

Emergent Theme #7: Impact of Working on Rest Days Towards Personality

Interview Question: Have you ever had to sacrifice personal plans on the weekend to catch up with your work? What do you think is this impact on your personality?

Participants	Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning
1	“Of course, there will be time that my personal plans would be in conflict with my. work schedule, I know it is inevitable that is why when situations as such come. I prioritize myself” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Lines 65-67)	Prioritizing self before the conflict
2	“syempre may mga personal plans talaga nasasacrifice minsan pero not to the extent where I am really stressed kasi i normally try to finish everything sa working hours para sa weekends i have time for my family.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Lines 48-50)	Sacrifices are inevitable but manageable
3	“oo ano uhh kadalasan lalo na kapag may OT sa work like overtime minsan kahit rest day ko pumapasok pa rin ako kasi iniisip ko sayang yung extrang pera, kita ganun tapos	Sacrifice for extra pay

	siguro ano masama siya sa pag-balance ko like myself and other uhh gawain ko sa buhay” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Lines 44-47)	
4	“definitely it was so frustrating that I had to catch up with my work when at that moment all I wanted was to take the day off you know and take a breather from all the stress and work loads During that moment, I was so stressed and irritated” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Lines 40-42)	Frustration due to lack of rest
5	“Maraming beses lalo na kapag may utos yung supervisor ko. Nagiging stressed and anxious ako kasi hindi ko maiwasan isipin pano” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Lines 30-31)	Sacrificed on personal plans for work orders.
6	“I have definitely had to give up some of my personal plans on the weekends in order to catch up with my work. I believe this kind of self-discipline can have a positive impact on my personality, as it teaches me the importance of planning and prioritizing.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Lines 57-59)	Sacrifice on personal plans to catch up with work yet views it as a sense of responsibility.
7	“I always make sure to make my professional work are done only business hours and days, this resulted for me being more vigilant to time and quality of my work. Some of my friends and colleagues are proud of how I manage both my career and personal life.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Lines 36-39)	Time management and being work-oriented is the key to enjoy and have free time for oneself.
8	“Hindi naman po siguro Not that much, kase yung my company na pinagtrabahuan ko is a people-first company”(Participant 8, Transcript H, Lines 28-29)	Do not sacrifice plans to catch up with work.
9	“I spare enough time for me to be able to rest. So, I believe that weekends should be for myself and my family.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Lines 29-30)	Respondents were able to enjoy the weekend and give rest for themselves, and bonding with family.
10	“Yes, I have. This may have effects on my personality as I can recall that I am very irritated in times when work ruins my personal plans. But the thing is, this is a responsibility that I have as a breadwinner.” (Participant 10, Transcript I, Lines 35-37)	Sacrifice on a personal plan yet views this as a responsibility shaping accountability trait.
11	“Wala naman, dahil parehas kami ng mga friends ko na breadwinners, and inadjust namin schedule namin kapag may isang busy o hindi makakapunta. In terms of my personality, feeling ko mas naging patient and understanding ako sa ibang tao.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 25-27)	Personal plans are not sacrificed for work. This developed a personality of patience and understanding.
12	”Yes. It made me more resilient but at the same time restless and pessimistic.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 29)	Sacrificing personal plans made me resilient but also anxious.
13	“A few times but my work is important to me so I think it is okay. I think it made me more responsible and do things on time” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Lines 25-26)	Sacrificing personal plans for work obligations.
14	“Of course, especially at the end of the month. Impact? Wala naman” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 22)	personal plans is a sacrifice to be able to catch up in work and It doesn't have an impact on personality.
15	“never n-no, my work requires weekdays.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Lines 67)	personal plans were not sacrificed for work

Naturally, due to their sexuality's deviation from the norm, members of the LGBT community have had to endure and adjust to a lot of sacrifices, from big things to small details. In the Philippines, where traditions and values dictate such lifestyles, members of the LGBT endured physical abuse, threats, and verbal insults, forced to change their fashion sense by their parental figures just so they could fit in better in society (Ceperiano et al., 2016). On top of the usual sacrifices, they are also not exempt from the sacrifices expected to be made by an employee of a company, particularly in our day and age. Due to the increasing shift to digital platforms, it is easier than ever before to keep in contact with your superiors, produce and submit outputs, and delegate tasks with a press of a button on our phones. This inquiry is about how prevalent that phenomenon is in the lives of LGBT employees. Everybody, at some point in their lives, has had to sacrifice personal time for an urgent errand or task for school or for work. However, the researchers would like to know if this phenomenon is the rule or the exception in their work lives. A total of 10 respondents answered that they had to sacrifice some of their personal time for work. Six of the respondents stated that from their sacrifice, they developed a sense of accountability on their part.

“Maraming beses lalo na kapag may utos yung supervisor ko. Nagiging stressed and anxious ako kasi hindi ko maiwasan isipin pano.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Lines 30-31)

Five respondents reported that they do not sacrifice personal plans for work as a sense of self-prioritization, which could be translated into work-life balance management.

“I always make sure to make my professional work are done only business hours and days, this resulted for me being more vigilant to time and quality of my work. Some of my friends and colleagues are proud of how I manage both my career and personal life.”

(Participant 7, Transcript G, Lines 36-39)

Two respondents said that they have had to sacrifice personal plans overwork, and it affects their stress level, which leads to anxious traits such as frustration and irritability.

“definitely it was so frustrating that I had to catch up with my work when at that moment all I wanted was to take the day off you know and take a breather from all the stress and work loads During that moment, I was so stressed and irritated.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Lines 40-42)

One respondent has sacrificed personal plans over work, believing that work is a responsibility they are obligated to fulfill.

Therefore, working reinforced their understanding and patience.

“Wala naman, dahil parehas kami ng mga friends ko na breadwinners, and inadjust namin schedule namin kapag may isang busy o hindi makakapunta. In terms of my personality, feeling ko mas naging patient and understanding ako sa ibang tao.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 25-27)

The last respondent stated that they do not feel an impact on their personality even with sacrificing personal plans on the weekend for work-related engagements.

“Of course, especially at the end of the month. Impact? Wala naman” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Lines 51-52)

The data obtained from this question is already an answer to the research question asking about the relation between working and the formation of their personalities. The respondents, confident enough with their answers, are vital to answering the question as we can see how varying personalities arise from the same stressful situation, they are each put under.

Emergent Theme #8: Accumulated Work Hours Per Week and its Impact on Personal Life

Interview Question: How many hours per week do you work on average? Does it ever get in the way of your personal life?

Participants	Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning
1	“at least 48 hours talagang oo, kinakain din naman siya kaso you know willingness lang naman din and as much as possible” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Lines 59-60)	Working 48 hours per week it's affecting personal life but it's manageable
2	“On average around 48 hours a week. Yeah, of course, work does get in the way in my personal life lalo na sa hobbies or maybe spending time with friends pero manageable naman siya.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Lines 10-12)	Working \geq 48 hours per week, negative effect in work-life balance
3	mga 48 hours ganun kadalasan kasi pinapasok ko isang rest day ko para mas malaki sahod ko then yung ibang friends ko ano nakakalabas sila date, pahinga sa weekends pero ako nasa trabaho pa rin wala eh kailangan (chuckles). (Participant 3, Transcript C, Lines 51-53)	Working \geq 48 hours per week has a negative effect on work-life balance
4	30-40 hrs per week but lately I'm accumulating until 50 hrs. It does take a lot of time, lot of me time. Because I would rather sleep than go out, socialize, or interact with my friends, (Participant 4, Transcript D, Lines 48-50)	Works 30-50 hrs per week; work-life is not balanced
5	“60 kasama na siguro yung mga overtime work at utos sa labas ng work hours. Kadalasan pero 35 ang naggive up ko ay pagayos sa bahay” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Lines 34-35)	Average working time for more than 40 hours per week. Work orders usually gets in the way when doing household responsibilities.
6	“On average, I work about 20-30 hours per week. But, it rarely interferes with my personal life. I'm very careful to make sure I'm taking time for myself and my family.” (Participant 6, Transcript D, Lines 64-65)	Average working time is below 40 hours per week. Rarely get in the way of personal life.
7	“I am at my work place at least 45 hours a week and if we exclude the lunch breaks it would be total of 40hrs per week” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Lines 44-45)	Working 40 hrs per week is able to enjoy my personal life and have a quality bonding with family.
8	40-50 hours hindi naman po siya nakaapekto sa personal life ko (Participant 8, Transcript H, Lines 33)	Average of more than 40 hours per week. Work rarely gets in the way of personal life.
9	“8-10 hours. Of course, it does.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Lines line 35)	8-10 hrs a day being an employee makes you feel tired and exhausted.
10	“an average of 50 hours po, hindi naman ito nakaka-sagabal sa personal plans ko.”	Work more than or equal to 40

	(Participant 10, Transcript J, Lines 40-41)	hours per week, and it does not affect personal life
11	“40-50 hours doesn't really affect my personal life” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Lines 30)	40 average work hours weekly. This does not hinder personal life.
12	“before I did (sacrificed personal time for work) but I see to it that It must not happen again it will take its toll on my health. 45-50 hours” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 32-33)	45-50 average working hours weekly. Does not hinder personal life.
13	“40 hours there are times when it gets in my personal life and I cannot do anything about it so I just have to finish my job before going out” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Lines 30-31)	Average of 40 work hours per week. Work sometimes affects personal life, but it is an obligation to fulfill.
14	“Probably 8 hrs?” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 25)	Having 8 hrs per day of working and still having time for yourself.
15	“I work for only 45 hours a week. My work is very flexible so it does not affect my personal life.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 71-72)	Working 45 hours a week does not affect personal life

The next inquiry is about the work hours of the respondents. Even though there have been a lot of studies conducted already on the positive impact of a well-thought-out window time for working and productivity, such as higher yields and profits, competitive salary opportunities, low turnover rate, and low overhead, private companies, and organizations still ignore the data and allow or at least turn a blind eye to after work-hours employee inquiries (Dhas, 2015). Of course, the standard is a minimum of eight hours for any law-abiding organization. The question was posed with overtime work and extra tasks done in preparation for their work, along with how that affects their personal life. The results were conclusive of the fact that the majority of them work beyond the set standard of 40 hours. 10 of the responses can be classified as the group who are towards working more than 40 hours per week, the reasons and attitude on the matter depend from person to person such as the need to earn money, or it's just a natural way of life for them. Seven of the said respondents said to have a negative impact on their personal life due to their sacrifice.

“30-40 hrs per week but lately I'm accumulating until 50 hrs. It does take a lot of time, lot of me time. Because I would rather sleep than go out, socialize, or interact with my friends.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Lines 48-50)

Four of those work beyond 40 hours. However, it is stated that their working hours do not effectively impact their personal lives.

“Before I did (sacrificed personal time for work) but I see to it that It must not happen again it will take its toll on my health. 45-50 hours.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 32-33)

Two respondents who do not work more than 40 hours per week reported that they could feel the impact on their personal lives due to their work schedule. However, it is a rare occurrence.

“40-50 hours hindi naman po siya nakaapekto sa personal life ko” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Lines 33)

The last two respondents who are also working less than or equal to 40 hours per week said that it does not affect their personal lives at all.

“I am at my work place at least 45 hours a week and if we exclude the lunch breaks it would be total of 40 hrs per week.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Lines 44-45)

The amount of time put into work is, of course, very influential to the mental well-being of any individual. Based on the data obtained, there may be some individuals who are alright managing such scenarios wherein they are expected to put in more than expected but also carry it with grace. However, such an underwhelming number supports the fact that working more is equivalent to the accumulation of more stress, which is very much impactful towards the development of any individual's personality.

Emergent Theme #9: Level of Difficulty in Breadwinning Obligations

Interview Question: How difficult or easy do you find it to be comfortable at work because of your personal obligations as a breadwinning homosexual?

Participants	Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning
1	“In terms of my obligation naman as a breadwinning uhg homosexual at work I don't find it difficult because the environment is so comfortable uhm... My family there naman to support me and accept me for who i am kaya mas napadali para sakin” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Line 71-74)	Positive work environment and family support
2	“I'd say in the middle. It depends on how you socialize with other people too. (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 58)”	Neutral in socializing with other people
3	“sa work ko naman very open naman kasi doon sa call center na pinapasukan ko pagdating sa sexuality okay lang sila eh like wala naman judgement may mga katrabaho ako na homosexual rin ganun din. Parang nagkakaintindihan kami at some point then siguro may discrimination and bad joke paminsan-minsan pero hindi ko na lang	Accepting work environment

4	pinapansin” (Participant 3 Transcript C, Line 57-61) “No matter how stressful the workload is, I can say that I am myself when I’m at work. It is just hard to be a breadwinner because you have to keep up with the expenses at home and everyone, almost everyone relies on you to bring food to the table.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 59-62)	It's easy and comfortable at work, but having some trouble at home
5	“Difficult kase hindi pa ko out sa workmates ko ang alam lang nila breadwinner ako” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 39)	Difficulty because of hidden sexuality
6	“Depending on the work environment and the people around you, it can be both easy and difficult to be comfortable at work as a breadwinning homosexual.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 71-72)	Comfortability at work depends on the environment.
7	“I find my role to be difficult, but since I love what I am doing this made me motivated to reach what I want in life” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 49-50)	Being passionate at work can make you happy, and on the other side, there are difficulties that you need to face.
8	“It's really hard po talaga, since some company tends to discriminate” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 38)	The industry, where inclusivity makes it more comfortable than other companies where discrimination exists.
9	“I must say it really depends on the situation.” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Lines 40)	Respondents feel easy or difficult depending on the situation but not at the point of struggling.
10	“Being a breadwinner is definitely difficult. It takes courage and sacrifice to be a breadwinner..” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Line 45)	Breadwinning is a difficult obligation that requires a strong personality.
11	“Easy dahil nakakausap ko at kalog mga co-workers ko. Alam din nila na breadwinner ako at naiintindihan nila ang estado ko. Wala naman silang problema sa sexuality ko.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Line 33-34)	Work is easy. The workplace is gender inclusive
12	“Easy if you’re working in the BPO industry where diversity is implemented.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 36)	Work is easy if the company is diverse.
13	“It is easy but its just that I have to be mindful of what I say and how I behave because others dont like noisy gays so there I just have to be decent so that people will not think I am like other” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Line 34-36)	Easy to be mindful and decent to other people
14	“it's not difficult or easy, it's just right because somehow, I can adapt to them and they can adapt to me because they know what I am.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Line 28-29)	The respondent is comfortable because the workplace is fair to all employees.
15	“It’s not difficult at all. My work is gender inclusive and we have a zero discrimination policy so that’s really nice.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 75-76)	the workplace is open to sexuality and is gender inclusive, which results to zero-discrimination

For the next avenue of their lived experiences, the researchers posed a question about their appropriate comfort and peace of mind at work for them to be able to accomplish their tasks efficiently with their obligations to their families in mind. The ground zero for employee peace of mind and comfort is at work, of course. It is imperative for a company to take care of its employees and LGBT employees more so. In general, employees tend to perform well if they are satisfied with their benefits and compensation. Both play a huge role in employees' commitment to the organization (Kim & Ryu, 2017). A majority of the respondents stated that it was easy for them due to the support and inclusion their colleagues provide them, given that they are the main financial proponents of their respective families as well as managing their social circles properly. Five responded that it was easy for them because their friends said they were comfortable with their work and that it was open to sexuality, gender inclusion, and zero discrimination.

“ano sa work ko naman very open naman kasi doon sa call center na pinapasukan ko pagdating sa sexuality okay lang sila eh like wala naman judgement may mga katrabaho ko na homosexual rin ganun din. Parang nagkakaintindihan kami at some point then siguro may discrimination and bad joke paminsan-minsan pero hindi ko na lang pinapansin.” (Participant 3 Transcript C, Line 57-61)

4 out of the 15 respondents said it depends on the social atmosphere and work environment, they also mentioned how sometimes it’s easy and sometimes it’s hard for them to be an homosexual breadwinner.

“Depending on the work environment and the people around you, it can be both easy and difficult to be comfortable at work as a breadwinning homosexual.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 71-72)

3 out of 15 respondents have it mixed. They have difficulties being comfortable at work because of personal obligations as a homosexual male breadwinner.

“Difficult kase hindi pa ko out sa workmates ko ang alam lang nila breadwinner ako.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 39)

One respondent reported it to be difficult to be comfortable at home but relaxing and comfortable to be at work.

“uhm.. no matter how stressful the workload is, I can say that I am myself when I’m at work. It is just hard to be a breadwinner because you have to keep up with the expenses at home and everyone, almost everyone relies on you to bring food to the table.” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 59-62)

One respondent found breadwinning obligation to be difficult but being passionate about work help to get through

“I find my role to be difficult but since I love what I am doing this made me motivated to reach what I want in life” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 49-50)

The last respondent recommends that if there is diversity in the workplace, it would be easier.

“Easy if you’re working in the BPO industry where diversity is implemented.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 36)

The question posed can be attributed mostly to the sub-question about their perception of their work, life, and identity formation. Like most of the answers that are inclined towards the impact of each three facets of life and how they influence one another, they each play a role and have differing effects on one another. Comfort is the key to this question, comfort being the ideal place wherein individuals can explore and express their personalities.

Emergent Theme #10: Financial Satisfaction in Work Pay

Interview Question: Is your work pay enough to shoulder your personal and family needs?

Participants	Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning
1	“ho-honestly talaga it’s not enough for both ano para saakin and for my family sako lang siya ano sa basic sa bahay like shelter, food, lights and everything pero ano hindi sya enough sa financial goals ko to be honest lang” (Participant 1, Transcript A, Lines 76-79)	Not enough for financial goals
2	“Average lang siya enough to sustain basic needs.” (Participant 2, Transcript B, Line 60)	Enough for basic needs
3	“yung totoo hindi. (chuckles) pero ano sa call center lang kasi like mas malaki yung pay compared to other jobs, then need ko rin like magtiis kasi nga madaming bayarin lalo na sa mga kapatid ko, ayun tiis-tiis lang.” (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 65-67)	Enduring to sustain family needs
4	“It is enough to bring food to the table like I said before, but uhm in terms of my future I don’t think it’s enough” (Participant 4, Transcript D, Line 65-66)	Work pay is enough to feed the family but not for the future
5	“hindi po sya enough for me and for us since madami po kaming needs at bills na bayarin.” (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 42-43)	Work pay is not enough for personal and family needs.
6	“my income is not enough to cater my family needs.” (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 76-77)	Work pay is not enough to cater to family needs.
7	“I am managing me and my family finances and today that I am taking some risk by entering some investments I am proud to say that it was enough however I can't deny that having more money is not that bad.” (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 55-57)	The work pay is enough to be able to provide for the needs of the family and personal wants.
8	“it's barely enough naman po to provide for my family's needs.” (Participant 8, Transcript H, Line 42)	Work pay is barely enough to provide for the family's needs.
9	“I would say it is enough because my family gets to eat decent food enough for them” (Participant 9, Transcript I, Line 44)	The work pay is enough to provide for the needs of the family.
10	“Yes, it is enough, but savings is not enough for emergency funds.” (Participant 10, Transcript J, Line 49)	Work pay is enough for family needs but no personal savings.
11	“Honestly, hindi dahil madalas ako mag-loan para mabigay ang kanilang kailangan at kagustuhan.” (Participant 11, Transcript K, Line 36- 37)	Work pay is not enough for personal and family needs.
12	“Right now my financial need is stable both for personal and family needs.” (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 38)	Work pay is enough for both personal and family needs.
13	“I think it is enough right now” (Participant 13, Transcript M, Line 38-39)	Work pay is enough for both personal and family needs.
14	“Yes, I earn enough to provide for my family's needs and also my needs.” (Participant 14, Transcript N, Lines 32)	The respondent's work pay is enough to provide family’s needs and savings for themself.
15	“I must say it really depends on the situation.” (Participant 15, Transcript O, Line 40)	The work pay is enough to provide for the needs of the family.

Financial Satisfaction in Work Pay

Understanding economic insecurity disparities is important for understanding the overall well-being of sexual minorities in the United States and elsewhere. Economic security involves more than just individual employment income; income from other sources, especially partners, views about well-being, and financial satisfaction all contribute to a person’s well-being (Chai and Maroto 2019). Finance is

a major factor in any working person's consideration for work and career, and this goes double for breadwinners whose failure to comply with their obligations might mean drastic repercussions whether it be on leisure and luxury, utilities, academics, it might even mean the difference between being hungry and satiated. It is also not unheard of for LGBT folk to be naturally diligent and keep one's financial stability and compensation in mind when putting in effort and time at work. In general, it is poverty that drives LGBT workers to strive even harder. Also factoring in the rising prices of commodities and the worsening of the economic situation (Sanchez S. 2021). The researchers posed this question as such because it has already been established that there is a certain tendency for LGBT folk just by virtue of their sexuality due to discrimination. Eight of the respondents claimed that their work pay is enough for their family's needs, but they can't save for personal savings. Five of them stated that they earned just enough to get by. Yielding just enough for their personal and family needs.

"I am managing me and my family finances and today that I am taking some risk by entering some investments, I am proud to say that it was enough. However, I can't deny that having more money is not that bad." (Participant 7, Transcript G, Line 55-57)

While four respondents said that their work pay isn't enough for their family's needs and also for their personal needs because of high expenses, more so to have extra money for luxuries and leisure.

"yung totoo hindi. (chuckles) pero ano sa call center lang kasi like mas malaki yung pay compared to other jobs, then need ko rin like magtiis kasi nga madaming bayarin lalo na sa mga kapatid ko, ayun tiis-tiis lang." (Participant 3, Transcript C, Line 65-67)

Only three of the respondents stated that their pay is enough for both their family's needs and enough to meet their financial goals.

"Yes, right now my financial need is stable both for personal and family needs." (Participant 12, Transcript L, Lines 38)

Two respondents mentioned how their earnings aren't enough for both their basic needs and financial goals.

"Hindi po sya enough for me and for us since madami po kaming needs at bills na bayarin." (Participant 5, Transcript E, Line 42-43)

Lastly, the remaining respondent reported that even though they are working for their family, their salary isn't enough to shoulder both personal and family expenses.

"That my income is not enough to cater my family needs." (Participant 6, Transcript F, Line 76-77)

There is no doubt that finances and the sufficiency of resources in that manner are integral to the role and duties of a breadwinner. Their success or failure may result in a massive impact on their confidence. In contrast, there are still a lot of nuances when it comes to finances and the different factors that come into play, such as the amount of effort put in, amount of time spent, mental strain, support, etc. it still depends on the individual and how they manage their respective situations. One thing is for sure. Financial success will alleviate most of the stress and anxiety one will get from just working.

Exhaustive Description and Fundamental Statement of Structure

Through the research done through interviews and data gathering on the lived experiences of Filipino breadwinning homosexual males, the researchers have come to conclude a lot of common themes among the respondents, even with their varying backgrounds. Also, the hardships and blessings that they consider also vary depending on their situation in life as of the present. From the emergent themes from each question, there are a lot of nuances between their responses, but also a lot of factors that are alike with one another.

The First avenue of discussion that would be presented with backing data is the treatment, view, and opinion of their families toward them from the perspective of their self-concept. It is not at all surprising that families and the generation of parents in the present are still apprehensive about homosexuality, living in a conventionally religious country with backing traditions that aren't LGBT-friendly. A couple of them, due to the fact that they've taken up responsibilities in their families, have had an increase in the degree of respect they felt from their families. However, it can still be argued that one does not need to take up such a heavy burden to be accepted by the family. That kind of love should come naturally.

The next item would be the impact of their taken-up obligations towards their self-identity, and the results are overwhelmingly bearable in nature. With their sexuality in mind, their self-development and maturation seem to be on par with that of a heterosexual breadwinner in a way that the maturity that comes with obligations is inevitable and is ultimately inconsequential to their self-identity. On a more positive note, only three of the respondents have stated discrimination towards them in their workplace.

Of course, family is an integral part of Filipino values. When asked about the topic, more than half of the respondents stated that they have their families at the center of their lives. The next chunk of the respondents takes a more individualistic approach wherein the challenges that they face only serve to make them stronger. As is with the majority of Filipinos, family is still the center of their values.

Being a homosexual in the workplace seems like an extra burden or cause of caution, especially on the topic of safety and well-being in a place where they could be found regularly. It is a relief to find out that only 7 out of 15 of the respondents opened up about a more negative experience in their workplace, whereas the rest of them reported that either the fact doesn't bother them or they have felt acceptance in the workplace. Most of the time, such individuals are targets for harassment; however, the air is shifting, and the Philippines is becoming more open by the day.

The next loaded question asked of the respondents is if their sexuality is an additional source of satisfaction and/or frustration. The researchers posed this question because of the usually black-and-white treatment Filipinos have towards members of the LGBT community. Black being the negative encounters wherein they face discrimination, judgment, harassment, etc. While being a more enjoyable outlook people have on them, as is with most Filipinos towards gay men, particularly in the entertainment industry. 12 respondents said that they feel satisfaction carrying their sexuality on top of their obligations which could be interpreted as a more welcoming approach towards them by their colleagues. Only 3 have had a minimally negative experience carrying both their sexuality and obligations to their families.

The sixth item is about the values they hold onto in order to keep going in life with their responsibilities and sanity balanced. A positive mindset is what most of them answered; however, this is not clear if it's toxic or not. Toxic in a way that they brush off their stress and negative feelings just so they can ignore them and feel more positive about their obligations. A healthy processing of emotions is still the best way to go about any kind of constant stress. Time management, taking off time, self-care, and faith is what the rest of the respondents hold onto. Fair values as they are proper coping mechanisms without any harm that may come with them.

In a capitalist society, a worker can expect to be wrung to their limit by the workload or superiors to get the most out of them in terms of work and output. Homosexual breadwinning males are no exemption. More than half of the respondents stated that they sacrifice leisure time for work and responsibilities on a regular, which is obviously a harder hit in terms of stress gained from work. In a perfect world, the work ends as soon as you clock out, but the opposite has become the norm in today's society, particularly because of the fast evolution of technology wherein staying connected is the expectation because communication nowadays is very ergonomic and convenient.

In line with the last item, working overtime is also another chore most employees have no choice but to agree to. It has become the norm as well, and it comes to show that even the respondents also work more than the suggested average work hours. More than half stated that they work more than 40 hours a week, and a big portion of them believe that it is a personal choice and not at all an additional obligation because they can say no. We have to keep in mind the standards of living in our society wherein the majority of jobs out there worked by the majority of the population don't pay enough for a comfortable life. People may say that it is their choice to work more, but ultimately the motive behind it is desperation to provide more for their family or self-indulgence. Neither of these is supposed to be achieved only by working one's self to the bone.

The grand question out of all the questions. An inquiry about their comfortability at work with their obligations and sexuality in the picture. Again, revisiting a prior question in the same line, only a portion of them reported experiences related to discrimination and difficulties. The respondents who answered more positively, that is, in a more accepting and welcoming attitude toward them, are more than those who answered with discrimination. An interpretation that stokes hope because it is an indication of the progress society has in terms of accepting LGBT folks fully and without question.

Finally, in terms of monetary status and financial security, as breadwinners, it is of utmost importance to them. The worker's situation in the Philippines isn't that very good. Government policies are still lagging compared to neighboring countries, and there are still a lot of discrepancies in pay and, of course, rampant corruption. All of which contribute to the financial satisfaction of those who are below them, which is looking dire. To live comfortably, being able to put food on the table as well as having leftovers for savings are the two things that enable such a life. Only eight respondents are financially comfortable. The rest of the respondents fall under either barely enough to get by or getting by but not comfortable enough.

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions drawn from the findings of this study's objectives:

Exploring the lived experience of Filipino homosexual male breadwinners adapting Collaizzi's descriptive phenomenological approach guided the researchers to extract significant statements, formulate meanings and organize into clusters, then emergent themes. These themes provided a detailed explanation and organization of the shared experiences of the phenomenon. The researchers trust the findings of this study that it captured the lived experiences of the participants.

Being a breadwinner entails an obligation to meet family needs. This is a responsibility that all breadwinners have in general. This role may be frustrating and hard sometimes, but various participants stressed that it is one satisfying feeling that led to their confidence, strong personality, independence, and self-worth.

A few participants expressed that discrimination is still present, but on a positive note, Filipinos, in general, are more open to establishing a sense of belongingness to homosexual males, which led several participants to enhance their social skills and a boost in self-expression in terms of sexuality in the workplace.

The results of this study found that the lived experience of homosexual male breadwinners indeed has an established relationship between identity formation and work-life balance.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study discussed, several recommendations are made:

The descriptive data presented in this study's findings may be utilized for future areas of research. By extending this study, other researchers might develop fresh theories and hypotheses to improve the opportunities for breadwinners in general and the LGBTQ+ community.

Implications for implementation and development of policymakers and private sector industries: The government and private industries may utilize the findings of this research for the opportunities and benefits of homosexual male careers. Future researchers may look into whether the duration of homosexual male breadwinners in employment affects their workplace acceptability.

Foster a better community embracing change. As discrimination continues to go down in time, good progress in openness and gender equality continues to increase. Future researchers can assess in-depth data with regards to the decrease in the number of discrimination over time and use this study as supporting data that workplace acceptance of other genders has improved.

The data from this research may be used to guide community extension services in the academic field. Schools may conduct seminars and workshops with homosexual male speakers to provide thoughts on how we can be more open to various genders in the school setting. This will establish a rapport of gender inclusivity within the school community.

Communities, in general, may facilitate awareness campaign programs to promote inclusiveness and a safe environment for all genders. The lived experience of the participants of this study may serve as implications for possible topics of future campaign programs for any community.

Future research may explore the phenomenological experiences of other members of the LGBTQ+ community, workplace discrimination, and implications for policymakers both from the government and industry perspectives. This study did not specifically address the phenomenological experiences of various groups in the LGBTQ+ community, along with the ideal opportunities and support that the participants find lacking in their respective careers from their companies and the government.

Future research may refresh this study by considering a sample having ranges of genders, careers, and nationalities which are not presented in this study. Other variables such as gender, career, and nationality may have modified the result of this study. The cultural factor was not addressed in this study which may have greatly influenced the lived experience of homosexual male breadwinners.

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